

ANIPH AI predictive tool/D2.5

WP 2, T 2.5 Development of ANIPH AI predictive system and traceability tool

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Table of Contents

List of Figures	5
List of Tables	7
List of Abbreviations	8
Executive Summary.....	9
1 Introduction.....	10
2 Methodology	12
2.1 Overview of the Modelling Workflow.....	12
2.2 Model Development Methodology.....	13
2.2.1 Dataset Preparation and Feature Engineering.....	13
2.2.2 Algorithm Selection	14
2.2.3 Training Strategy.....	14
2.2.4 Model Evaluation and Explainability	14
2.2.5 Applicability Domain Assessment.....	15
2.2.6 Model Deployment.....	16
3 Results and Discussion.....	18
3.1 Thermal Property Models.....	18
3.1.1 Glass Transition Temperature (T_g) Model for PHBV polymers.....	18
3.1.2 T_g Model for mcl-PHA polymers	22
3.1.3 Melting Temperature (T_m) Model for PHBV polymers	26
3.1.4 T_m Model for mcl-PHA polymers	30
3.2 Mechanical and Rheological Models.....	36
3.2.1 Tensile Strength Model for PHBV polymers.....	36
3.2.2 Complex Viscosity Model for PHBV polymers	41
3.3 Biodegradation and Toxicity Models.....	47
3.3.1 Biodegradation Model for PHBV polymers	47
3.3.2 Ecotoxicity Model for PHBV polymers.....	51
3.3.3 Cytotoxicity Model for PHBV polymers	55
3.3.4 Toxicity Statistical Analysis for mcl-PHAs	58
4 Conclusions.....	61
5 References.....	63
6 Annexes	66
6.1 Annex 1 – Source Code and Processed Datasets for the ANIPH Predictive Models	66
6.2 Annex – 2 Jaqpot Access and Usage Instructions.....	66
6.2.1 Direct Access Links to ANIPH Models.....	66
6.2.2 Navigating the Jaqpot Platform.....	67

List of Figures

Figure 1. Comparison plot of the predicted T_g values from the model with the observed values in the training set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.	21
Figure 2. Comparison plot of the predicted T_g values from the model with the observed values in the test set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.	21
Figure 3. SHAP Summary Plot for T_g Model.	22
Figure 4. Comparison plot of the predicted T_g values from the model with the observed values in the training set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.	25
Figure 5. Comparison plot of the predicted T_g values from the model with the observed values in the test set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.	25
Figure 6. SHAP Summary Plot for T_g Model.	26
Figure 7. Comparison plot of the predicted T_m values from the model with the observed values in the training set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.	29
Figure 8. Comparison plot of the predicted T_m values from the model with the observed values in the test set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.	29
Figure 9. SHAP Summary Plot for T_m Model.	30
Figure 10. Comparison plot of the predicted T_m values from the model with the observed values in the training set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.	33
Figure 11. Comparison plot of the predicted T_m values from the model with the observed values in the test set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.	34
Figure 12. SHAP Summary Plot for T_g Model.	34
Figure 13. Distribution of Tensile Strength Values in the Initial Dataset.	37
Figure 14. Comparison plot of the predicted tensile strength values from the model with the observed values in the training set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.	39
Figure 15. Comparison plot of the predicted tensile strength values from the model with the observed values in the test set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.	40
Figure 16. SHAP Summary Plot for Tensile Strength Model.	41
Figure 17. Comparison plot of the predicted complex viscosity values from the model with the observed values in the training set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.	44
Figure 18. Comparison plot of the predicted complex viscosity values from the model with the observed values in the test set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.	45
Figure 19. SHAP Summary Plot for Complex Viscosity Model.	45

Figure 20. Comparison plot of the predicted biodegradation percentage values from the model with the observed values in the training set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.	49
Figure 21. Comparison plot of the predicted biodegradation percentage values from the model with the observed values in the test set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.	50
Figure 22. SHAP Summary Plot for Biodegradation Percentage Model	51
Figure 23. SHAP Summary Plot for Ecotoxicity Model.	54
Figure 24. SHAP Summary Plot for Cytotoxicity Model.	57
Figure 25. Distribution of toxicity and relationship with additive presence in mcl-PHA formulations. a) Overall toxicity profile of mcl-PHAs. b) Toxicity distribution in formulations containing additives c) Toxicity distribution in formulations without additives.	60
Figure 26. Cell viability comparison between toxic and non-toxic mcl-PHA formulations.	60

List of Tables

Table 1. Input Features Used in the T_g Model.	18
Table 2. Sample rows from the final T_g dataset.	19
Table 3. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for T_g Model.....	20
Table 4. Model T_g Performance.	20
Table 5. Input Features Used in the T_g Model.	22
Table 6. Sample rows from the final T_g dataset.	23
Table 7. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for T_g Model.....	24
Table 8. Model T_g Performance.	24
Table 9. Input Features Used in the T_m Model.....	26
Table 10. Sample rows from the final T_m dataset.....	27
Table 11. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for T_m Model.....	28
Table 12. Model T_m Performance	28
Table 13. Input Features Used in the T_m Model.....	30
Table 14. Sample rows from the final T_m dataset.....	32
Table 15. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for T_m Model.....	32
Table 16. Model T_m Performance.	33
Table 17. Input Features Used in the Tensile Strength Model.....	36
Table 18. Sample rows from the final Tensile Strength dataset.....	38
Table 19. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for Tensile Strength Model.....	38
Table 20. Model Tensile Strength Performance	39
Table 21. Input Features Used in the Complex Viscosity Model.....	41
Table 22. Sample rows from the final Complex Viscosity dataset.....	43
Table 23. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for Complex Viscosity Model.....	43
Table 24. Model Complex Viscosity Performance.....	44
Table 25. Input Features Used in the Biodegradation Percentage Model.....	47
Table 26. Sample rows from the final Biodegradation dataset.....	48
Table 27. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for Biodegradation Percentage Model.....	48
Table 28. Model Biodegradation Percentage Performance	49
Table 29. Input Features Used in the Ecotoxicity Model.....	52
Table 30. Sample rows from the final Ecotoxicity dataset.....	53
Table 31. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for Ecotoxicity Model.....	53
Table 32. Model Ecotoxicity Performance.....	53
Table 33. Input Features Used in the Cytotoxicity Model.....	55
Table 34. Sample rows from the final Cytotoxicity dataset.....	56
Table 35. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for Cytotoxicity Model.....	56
Table 36. Model Cytotoxicity Performance.....	56
Table 37. Descriptive statistics of polymer composition ratios and molecular weight parameters.....	59

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
ANIPH	Avoiding the Negative Impacts produced by Plastic materials in Humanitarian contexts
AUA	Agricultural University of Athens
AI	Artificial Intelligence
PHAs	Polyhydroxyalkanoates
PHBV	Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)
scl-PHAs	Short-Chain-Length Polyhydroxyalkanoates
3HB	3-Hydroxybutyrate
3HV	3-Hydroxyvalerate
ML	Machine Learning
Mw	Molecular Weight
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals
QSAR	Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship
mcl-PHAs	Medium-Chain-Length Polyhydroxyalkanoates
FAMD	Factorial Analysis of Mixed Data
IQR	Interquartile Range
RF	Random Forest
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
SHAP	Shapley Additive Explanations
RF	Random Forest
AD	Applicability Domain
T _g	Glass Transition Temperature
T _m	Melting Temperature
4HV	4-Hydroxyvalerate
3HHx	3-Hydroxyhexanoate
3HO	3-Hydroxyoctanoate
3HHp	3-Hydroxyheptanoate
3HN	3-Hydroxynonanoate
3HD	3-Hydroxydecanoate
3HDD	3-Hydroxydodecanoate

Executive Summary

The deliverable **D2.5: “ANIPH AI Predictive Tool”** presents the development, validation, and deployment of a suite of machine learning (ML) models designed to predict thermal, rheological, biodegradation, cytotoxicity and ecotoxicity properties of polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA)-based polymers within the ANIPH project. The models support Work Package 2 (WP2) and specifically Task T2.5.2, which focuses on the creation of AI-based predictive systems to minimize negative environmental impacts arising from plastic materials in humanitarian contexts.

Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV), a representative member of the polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs), is a biodegradable copolymer whose properties depend on factors such as hydroxyvalerate (HV) content, molecular weight (Mw), crystallinity, processing conditions, and the presence of additives. Experimental characterization of PHBV is time consuming and often impractical in urgent humanitarian environments. Therefore, computational predictive models offer a powerful alternative to accelerate material selection and risk assessment.

In this deliverable, a complete end-to-end modelling pipeline was developed, including data preprocessing, outlier detection, mixed data dimensionality reduction, model training, hyperparameter optimization, cross-validation, explainability analysis, and platform deployment.

A total of **nine predictive models** were created to estimate:

- *Glass transition temperature (T_g)*
- *Melting temperature (T_m)*
- *Complex viscosity*
- *Biodegradation percentage*
- *Cytotoxicity*
- *Ecotoxicity*

All predictive models demonstrated reliable performance, scientific consistency, and interpretability. The resulting Artificial Intelligence (AI) tool supports ANIPH’s mission by enabling informed and rapid decision making regarding biodegradable materials used in humanitarian contexts.

1 Introduction

Plastic pollution is a major environmental concern, particularly in humanitarian settings where waste management systems are often limited or temporarily disrupted (Jambeck et al., 2015). Biodegradable polymers such as PHAs represent promising alternatives, combining renewable biological origin with reduced environmental persistence (Sudesh, Abe and Doi, 2000). Among them, PHBV is a **short chain length (scl) PHA**, composed of 3-hydroxybutyrate (3-HB) and 3-hydroxyvalerate (3-HV) monomer units which exhibits tunable thermal, mechanical, rheological and biodegradation properties depending on its HV content, Mw, crystallinity, and processing conditions (Rodríguez-Contreras, 2019; Koller, 2018).

However, PHAs on their own have several disadvantages, such as high production cost, limited functional performance, incompatibility with conventional thermal processing techniques and susceptibility to thermal degradation (Li, Yang & Loh, 2016). To overcome these limitations and ensure the desirable and optimal physicochemical properties and functional performance of the materials, understanding the factors influencing them is crucial. Additionally, lowering the production cost of PHAs is necessary to make them competitive with conventional plastics.

Recent advances in polymer informatics show that ML approaches can capture complex structure-property relationships and significantly accelerate the development of polymer materials (Ramprasad et al., 2017; Chen, Pilania and Ramprasad, 2021). In this context, computational modelling is an especially valuable tool for **ANIPH**, since ML models can support rapid discovery and design of materials (Ma & Luo, 2020).

Especially for PHAs, they offer several advantages. Firstly, they accelerate material selection and reduce dependency on slow experimental characterization. Formulation optimization is supported by identifying influential properties such as HV content or Mw. Moreover, they enable pre-screening of candidate additives to assess how they may enhance or modify PHBV properties, particularly biodegradation and toxicity performance, prior to laboratory validation. Finally, interpretable insights into how structural, or processing variables influence material behavior are provided. Such capabilities are essential in humanitarian contexts, where materials must be evaluated rapidly for suitability, safety, and environmental compatibility.

In accordance to the European Regulation (European Parliament and Council, 2006) for Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) (European Parliament and Council, 2006), data-driven computational approaches such as **Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR)**, Grouping and Read-Across are promoted as alternative methods to animal testing (European Chemicals Agency, 2017). QSARs are mathematical, data-driven predictive models, which are developed on the assumption that the chemical (molecular) structures of substances affect several endpoints of interest that can be defined and measured (Puzyn et al., 2018). These endpoints may include physicochemical properties, (eco)toxicological

or biodegradation behavior, and environmental fate parameters that, being measurable, can be modelled. Molecular and material structures are quantitatively represented by molecular descriptors, which may be either experimentally measured properties (physicochemical, bioactivity) or theoretical calculations of molecules' properties that are generated by algorithms. These descriptors form the essential data backbone of predictive modeling, allowing relationships between structure and activity (or performance) to be established. High quality characterization data is a prerequisite for the successful development of any data-driven QSAR method, which was a key focus of ANIPH Deliverable **D2.8**.

The datasets of **D2.8** were used as raw data for the development of QSAR-based ML models for the prediction of scl-PHAs and medium chain length PHAs (mcl-PHAs) properties (rheological, mechanical, thermal), safety profiles (ecotoxicity) and biodegradation behavior of the proposed materials, formulations and products. Several advancements have been made as enhancement of the accuracy and practicality of QSAR modelling, facing the degradation process from a multi-scale perspective (from the molecular to the macroscopic scale), considering polymer characteristics (Mw, crystallinity, copolymer ratio, etc.), and anticipating how several important properties (e.g., elastic modulus, tensile strength) evolve as degradation reactions occur within the polymer chains.

Withing ANIPH, **AUA** developed predictive **QSAR models** that correlated the experimentally derived descriptors from data libraries with endpoints of interest (related to processability- such as mechanical and thermal properties-, toxicity and biodegradation percentages in soil, fresh water and marine environment) for the target biomaterials. Model development included selection of the appropriate respective algorithms, training the models, and validating their performance.

Deliverable **D2.5 "ANIPH AI Predictive Tool"** documented the complete development of a ML model designed to predict key thermal, rheological, degradation, and toxicity properties of **PHA-based polymers** relevant to the ANIPH project. The scope of this deliverable covers the entire modelling workflow, from initial data preparation to final deployment on the Jaqpot platform (<https://jaqpot.org>), ensuring full transparency, traceability and reproducibility.

2 Methodology

This section outlines the methodological framework used for the development, training, and evaluation of predictive models within the ANIPH project. The objective was to create reliable ML models capable of predicting thermal, rheological, mechanical, biodegradation and toxicity properties of PHAs using small-to-medium sized experimental datasets. The workflow included several key components: **dataset preparation, feature-space construction, algorithm selection, training strategy, and model evaluation**. All models were implemented in scikit-learn and deployed on the Jaqpot platform (<https://jaqpot.org>), ensuring accessibility, reproducibility, and a user-friendly environment for interacting with the predictive tools.

2.1 Overview of the Modelling Workflow

The modelling pipeline consisted of the following key steps:

1. **Data collection, preprocessing and cleaning** to ensure consistency across all PHAs descriptors.
2. **Transformation of mixed numerical and categorical variables using Factorial Analysis of Mixed Data (FAMD)** to generate a unified latent feature space suitable for ML algorithms.
3. **Outlier detection and removal** using the **interquartile range (IQR) method** to improve model stability.
4. **Reconstruction of the latent feature space** using a second FAMD pass applied to the cleaned dataset, ensuring robust representation of the descriptor space.
5. **Construction of training and test sets using the Kennard–Stone algorithm**, ensuring uniform coverage of the latent descriptor space.
6. **Model development using Random Forest (RF) regression**, including hyperparameter optimization using GridSearchCV.
7. **Model evaluation** using training and test set metrics, including R-squared (R^2), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE).
8. **Robust validation using 5-fold or 10-fold cross-validation**, depending on dataset size.
9. **Explainability analysis using Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP)** to understand each feature contribution.
10. **Deployment and verification of the models on the Jaqpot platform**, enabling reproducible access for both partners and end-users.

2.2 Model Development Methodology

2.2.1 Dataset Preparation and Feature Engineering

The modelling pipeline began with the aggregation of experimental datasets describing physicochemical, thermal, mechanical, rheological, biodegradation and toxicity-related properties of PHBV and related PHA-based materials. The raw data also covered a diverse range of experimental variables including processing conditions, environmental parameters, as well as the presence, concentration and type of additives employed.

All datasets were subjected to a rigorous inspection process to ensure scientific consistency and reliability. This included the removal of duplicate entries, physically implausible values, inconsistent experimental records, and disparities introduced by different laboratory practices. Since the datasets comprised both numerical descriptors (e.g. Mw, temperature measurements) and categorical variables (such as experimental conditions, additive type), FAMD was employed to jointly embed all features into a unified latent space. FAMD is particularly well-suited for this scenario because it extends principal component approaches to handle mixed data types, enabling the extraction of the main sources of variability across both quantitative and qualitative variables. This integration facilitates dimensionality reduction and supports the development of ML models that can effectively leverage the complex, heterogeneous structure which is typical of polymer datasets (Pagès, 2014).

Outliers were identified and removed using the IQR method, which offers a robust, non-parametric approach for outlier detection that does not assume data normality and is less affected by skewness or imbalance in class representation (Tukey, 1977). The IQR method is particularly advantageous in heterogeneous and unbalanced datasets, where parametric alternatives such as Z-score thresholding may fail to accurately flag extreme values (Cousineau and Chartier, 2010). By excluding values lying beyond 1.5 times the IQR from the quartiles, this procedure minimizes the influence of outliers on subsequent analyses. After removing these outliers, a second FAMD transformation was conducted to recalculate the latent feature space, ensuring that the descriptor structure of the dataset remained representative and optimized for downstream modeling.

To maximize coverage of the feature space and minimize sampling bias, the dataset was partitioned into training and test subsets using the Kennard-Stone algorithm (Kennard and Stone, 1969). Unlike random sampling, the Kennard-Stone method sequentially selects samples that are maximally separated in multivariate space, resulting in subsets that uniformly represent the diversity of the data and support more generalizable model evaluation. This approach is particularly effective for complex and high-dimensional datasets, as it systematically ensures that all regions of the descriptor space are represented and avoids oversampling densely populated regions or neglecting rare but informative patterns.

2.2.2 Algorithm Selection

RF was chosen as the central predictive algorithm in this study due to its well-established advantages for handling polymer datasets, which are often small, heterogeneous, or high-dimensional. RF demonstrates strong predictive performance even with limited or imbalanced data, owing to its ensemble nature and internal bootstrapping mechanism (Breiman, 2001). By aggregating the outputs of multiple decorrelated decision trees, it exhibits low susceptibility to overfitting and can accurately capture complex, nonlinear relationships between polymer descriptors and targeted properties (Hastie, Tibshirani and Friedman, 2009). Furthermore, RF imposes minimal requirements on data preprocessing, such as feature scaling or normalization, streamlining the modeling pipeline (Pedregosa et al., 2011). Hyperparameter optimization in RF is computationally efficient, often requiring the adjustment of relatively few parameters. Importantly, the algorithm has demonstrated robust performance in various polymer informatics studies, further supporting its suitability for structure-property prediction tasks (Ramprasad et al., 2017)

2.2.3 Training Strategy

The cleaned datasets were partitioned into training (80%) and testing (20%) subsets. In cases where the target variable distribution was uneven (particularly in classification tasks), stratified splitting was employed to maintain representative proportions across all ranges, thereby mitigating sampling bias. Hyperparameter optimization was carried out using GridSearchCV combined with k-fold cross-validation (5-fold or 10-fold, depending on dataset size) to robustly evaluate model performance against unseen data. The tuned hyperparameters included:

- **number of trees** (`n_estimators`)
- **maximum tree depth** (`max_depth`)
- **minimum samples per split** (`min_samples_split`)
- **minimum samples per leaf** (`min_samples_leaf`)

Following the identification of optimal hyperparameters, the final RF model was retrained on the entire training dataset to maximize predictive capability prior to deployment.

2.2.4 Model Evaluation and Explainability

◇ Regression Models

Model performance for regression tasks was evaluated using:

- **R²** (coefficient of determination)
- **RMSE**

- **MAE**

These metrics collectively quantify explained variance, mean prediction errors, and average absolute deviations, enabling robust assessment of continuous prediction accuracy.

◇ Classification Models

For classification models, the following metrics were reported:

- **Accuracy**
- **Balanced accuracy**
- **Precision**
- **Recall**
- **F1 score**
- **Jaccard index**
- **Matthews correlation coefficient**

These metrics characterize various aspects of classification performance, including overall correctness (accuracy), proper balance across classes (balanced accuracy), relevance of positive predictions (precision), completeness (recall), and combined predictive power (F1 score, Jaccard index, Matthews coefficient), yielding a comprehensive evaluation of each model's discriminative ability.

Diagnostic visualizations, including predicted versus actual plots for both training and test datasets, were utilized to detect systematic errors, investigate the presence of heteroscedasticity, and identify potential underfitting, thereby supporting robust model evaluation and refinement.

To enhance interpretability, Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) were applied, allowing for feature-level attributions for each prediction. SHAP leverages cooperative game-theoretic principles to assign an importance value to each feature, clarifying the influence of individual polymer descriptors on predicted property outcomes (Lundberg and Lee, 2017). This approach supports deeper scientific insight into structure-property relationships and fosters trust in the model output.

2.2.5 Applicability Domain Assessment

Before deployment, each model underwent **Applicability Domain (AD)** analysis to evaluate whether new input samples fall within the descriptor space on which the model was trained. Assessing AD is essential to ensure that predictions are scientifically meaningful and not extrapolated beyond the model's reliable regions (OECD, 2014).

Three complementary AD methods were applied:

- Leverage Method**

The leverage method evaluates how far a new sample lies from the centroid of the training descriptor space. Where:

- **h**: leverage value of the sample
- **h***: threshold value determining influence

Samples with $h < h^*$ are considered within the AD, meaning their predictions are reliable.

ii. Bounding Box Method

The Bounding Box method evaluates whether each feature value of a new sample falls within the minimum and maximum range observed in the training dataset. If all features of the evaluated samples lie within this multidimensional hyper-rectangle, the sample is within the AD.

iii. Mean Variance (MeanVar) Method

The MeanVar method evaluates whether the multivariate distribution (mean and variance) of the new input is consistent within the statistical profile of the training dataset.

All the methods above provide a robust evaluation of whether a query sample lies within the model's validated domain. All models developed in ANIPH passed the internal AD verification tests, and AD results are returned to users dynamically through the Jaqpot interface.

2.2.6 Model Deployment

After the completion of model development, validation, interpretability analysis and applicability domain assessment, all final models were deployed on the **Jaqpot** platform (<https://jaqpot.org>), to ensure practical accessibility and reproducibility.

Jaqpot is a cloud-based environment designed for hosting, managing, and executing predictive models in chemistry, materials science, biotechnology, and toxicology. Deploying the ANIPH models on Jaqpot provides several key advantages:

- **Accessibility:** Users can run predictions directly through a simple web interface without the need for programming skills or local computational resources.
- **Reproducibility:** Each model and its associated metadata were systematically versioned, guaranteeing that predictions remain consistent across different users, computational environments, and points in time.
- **Transparency:** Model metadata, performance metrics, and applicability domain results are displayed for users, supporting informed decision-making.
- **Ease of use:** Inputs can be submitted through guided forms, prediction results are clearly presented, and applicability domain warnings are automatically returned.

Each model underwent automated verification within Jaqpot to confirm correct operation and consistent prediction behaviour before being made available to partners and end-users. Through this deployment strategy, the ANIPH predictive models are delivered as robust, user-friendly digital tools that support research, development, and industrial applications across the project domains. Additional supporting materials, including processed datasets, released code, and a user guide with screenshots from the Jaqpot platform, are provided in **Annexes 1 and 2**.

3 Results and Discussion

This section presents the performance and scientific interpretation of the ML models developed for predicting the thermal, mechanical, rheological, biodegradation, cytotoxicity and ecotoxicity properties of PHA-based materials. For each model, the dataset composition, feature set, predictive performance, AD behaviour, and key scientific insights are discussed.

3.1 Thermal Property Models

3.1.1 Glass Transition Temperature (T_g) Model for PHBV polymers

3.1.1.1 Dataset Composition and Input Features

This model was created to explore which physicochemical and formulation-related descriptors are suitable for predicting the glass transition temperature (T_g) of PHBV polymers. The following input features were included:

Table 1. Input Features Used in the T_g Model.

Category	Input Feature	Type	Units
Composition	3-hydroxybutyrate (3HB) percentage	Numerical	%
Composition	3-hydroxyvalerate (3HV) percentage	Numerical	%
Molecular properties	Weight-average molar mass (Mw) of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate, PHBV)	Numerical	g/mol
Structural properties	Crystallinity index	Numerical	%
Additives	Additive type	Categorical	-
Additives	Additive percentage	Numerical	%

The initial dataset consisted of **89 samples**. Outlier detection was performed using the IQR method, after which **67 samples** remained. The Kennard-Stone algorithm was then used to ensure an even coverage of the descriptor space. Following a standard 80/20 split:

- Training set: 53 samples
- Test set: 14 samples

Table 2 summarizes the structure of the final dataset used for evaluation of the T_g prediction model.

Table 2. Sample rows from the final T_g dataset.

HB_ratio	HV_ratio	Mw_PHBV	Additive1_type	Additive1_percentage	Crystallinity_index	Tg_final
100.0	0.0	440000.0	Compatibilizer	20.0	58.00	282.15
100.0	0.0	440000.0	Compatibilizer	40.0	53.00	288.15
98.0	2.0	280000.0	not_applicable	0.0	65.35	271.42
98.0	2.0	280000.0	Compatibilizer	1.0	63.34	271.43
100.0	0.0	760000.0	not_applicable	0.0	59.50	276.35
100.0	0.0	760000.0	Compatibilizer	0.0	58.40	282.45
100.0	0.0	760000.0	Compatibilizer	0.0	46.20	275.25
100.0	0.0	760000.0	Compatibilizer	0.0	49.30	275.05
100.0	0.0	760000.0	Compatibilizer	0.0	33.30	270.85
100.0	0.0	760000.0	Compatibilizer	0.0	27.10	272.15
100.0	0.0	440000.0	not_applicable	0.0	63.00	276.15
100.0	0.0	440000.0	Compatibilizer	10.0	68.80	280.15
100.0	0.0	440000.0	Compatibilizer	20.0	72.50	282.15
100.0	0.0	440000.0	Compatibilizer	40.0	88.00	288.15
100.0	0.0	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	50.80	271.85
92.0	8.0	443000.0	not_applicable	0.0	64.30	277.65
92.0	8.0	443000.0	Compatibilizer	10.0	62.40	278.65
100.0	0.0	1700000.0	not_applicable	0.0	27.30	268.65
100.0	0.0	1200000.0	not_applicable	0.0	28.00	272.35
100.0	0.0	1600000.0	not_applicable	0.0	47.00	276.15

3.1.1.2 Model Development and Hyperparameter Selection

A **RF Regressor** was used, implemented via Python and the following libraries:

- **jaqpotpy**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning
- **NumPy** and **Pandas**: for numerical operations and data manipulation
- **Scikit-learn**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning
- **prince**: for FAMD-based feature-space construction

The candidate parameter values, along with those selected based on the best cross-validation performance, are presented below in Table 3, while the model evaluation is presented in Table 4.

Table 3. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for T_g Model.

Hyperparameter	Candidate Values Tested	Optimal Value
n_estimators	[30, 50, 100, 200, 300]	300
max_depth	[None, 10, 20, 30]	None
min_samples_split	[2, 5, 10]	2
min_samples_leaf	[1, 2, 4, 5, 10]	1

Table 4. Model T_g Performance.

Predictions	Metric	Optimal Value
Train set	R ²	0.983
Test set		0.875
Cross validation 5-fold		0.835

The T_g prediction model demonstrated strong overall performance, with an excellent fit on the training set (**R² = 0.983**) and a solid generalization performance on the test set (**R² = 0.875**). The cross-validated R² value of **0.835** indicates that the model is stable across resampled subsets and not overly sensitive to data partitioning.

3.1.1.3 Plot Results

The following figures present the comparison between the model predictions and the experimental values for the training and test sets.

Figure 1. Comparison plot of the predicted T_g values from the model with the observed values in the training set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.

Figure 2. Comparison plot of the predicted T_g values from the model with the observed values in the test set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.

3.1.1.4 SHAP Explainability Analysis

SHAP analysis was performed to identify which descriptors influence the predicted T_g values as presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. SHAP Summary Plot for T_g Model.

The results highlight the **crystallinity index** as the dominant contributor: higher crystallinity consistently increases T_g , while lower values reduce it. **M_w** also shows a positive effect, with higher Mw associated with higher T_g due to reduced chain mobility. Overall, the SHAP results confirm that the model relies on physically meaningful structure–property relationships, reinforcing confidence in its predictive behaviour.

3.1.2 T_g Model for mcl-PHA polymers

3.1.2.1 Dataset Composition and Input Features

This model was created to explore which physicochemical and formulation-related descriptors are suitable for predicting the T_g of mcl-based PHA polymers. The following input features were included:

Table 5. Input Features Used in the T_g Model.

Category	Input Feature	Type	Units
Composition	Short-Chain-Length Monomer Ratio in PHA	Numerical	%
Composition	3-hydroxybutyrate (3HB) percentage	Numerical	%

Category	Input Feature	Type	Units
Composition	3-hydroxyvalerate (3HV) percentage	Numerical	%
Composition	Medium-Chain-Length Monomer Ratio in PHA	Numerical	%
Molecular properties	Weight-average molar mass (Mw) of PHA polymer	Numerical	g/mol
Structural properties	Polydispersity Index	Numerical	%

The initial dataset consisted of **296 samples**. Outlier detection was performed using the IQR method, after which **239 samples** remained. The Kennard-Stone algorithm was then used to ensure an even coverage of the descriptor space. Following a standard 80/20 split:

- Training set: 191 samples
- Test set: 48 samples

Table 6 summarizes the structure of the final dataset used for evaluation of the T_g prediction model.

Table 6. Sample rows from the final T_g dataset.

initial_scl_pha_ratio	initial_3hb_ratio	initial_3hv_ratio	initial_mcl_pha_ratio	mw	pdi	tg_final
2.00	0.00	2.0	98.00	40000.0	2.000000	232.65
0.00	0.00	0.0	100.00	151000.0	1.860000	227.15
0.00	0.00	0.0	100.00	124000.0	2.100000	224.75
0.00	0.00	0.0	100.00	145000.0	2.010000	226.85
0.00	0.00	0.0	100.00	110000.0	1.500000	226.15
0.00	0.00	0.0	100.00	175000.0	2.300000	239.15
0.00	0.00	0.0	100.00	206000.0	2.400000	233.15
0.00	0.00	0.0	100.00	286000.0	2.400000	240.05
99.10	99.10	0.0	0.90	260000.0	1.900000	280.15
5.04	5.04	0.0	94.95	91000.0	2.500000	288.45
0.20	0.20	0.0	99.80	85000.0	1.500000	234.15
0.00	0.00	0.0	100.00	57000.0	1.900000	231.75
0.00	0.00	0.0	100.00	32000.0	2.400000	228.05
0.00	0.00	0.0	100.00	68000.0	1.900000	230.25
0.00	0.00	0.0	100.00	62000.0	1.900000	226.45
0.00	0.00	0.0	100.00	102000.0	2.000000	226.15
0.00	0.00	0.0	100.00	546400.0	2.831088	236.06
0.00	0.00	0.0	100.00	666300.0	2.637767	235.44
0.00	0.00	0.0	100.00	707800.0	2.587934	234.88
0.00	0.00	0.0	100.00	658900.0	3.139114	234.77

3.1.2.2 Model Development and Hyperparameter Selection

A **RF Regressor** was used, implemented via Python and the following libraries:

- **jaqpotpy**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning
- **NumPy** and **Pandas**: for numerical operations and data manipulation
- **Scikit-learn**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning
- **prince**: for FAMD-based feature-space construction

The candidate parameter values, along with those selected based on the best cross-validation performance, as well as the model evaluation, are presented in the tables below.

Table 7. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for T_g Model.

Hyperparameter	Candidate Values Tested	Optimal Value
n_estimators	[30, 50, 100, 200, 300]	200
max_depth	[None, 10, 20, 30]	None
min_samples_split	[2, 5, 10]	10
min_samples_leaf	[1, 2, 4, 5, 10]	2

Table 8. Model T_g Performance.

Predictions	Metric	Optimal Value
Train set	R^2	0.896
Test set		0.855
Cross validation 10-fold		0.800

The T_g prediction model demonstrated robust and reliable performance. The training set R^2 value of **0.896** indicates that the model successfully captured the underlying structure-property relationships within the dataset. Its strong performance on the test set ($R^2 = \mathbf{0.855}$) confirms good generalization to unseen data, while the cross-validated R^2 of **0.800** shows that the model remains stable across different data partitions. Overall, these results suggest that the model is both accurate and resilient, with no signs of overfitting.

3.1.2.3 Plot Results

The following figures present the comparison between the model predictions and the experimental values for the training and test sets.

Figure 4. Comparison plot of the predicted T_g values from the model with the observed values in the training set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.

Figure 5. Comparison plot of the predicted T_g values from the model with the observed values in the test set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.

3.1.2.4 SHAP Explainability Analysis

SHAP analysis was performed to identify which descriptors influence the predicted T_g values as presented in the figure below.

Figure 6. SHAP Summary Plot for T_g Model.

The SHAP analysis shows that the key contributors to the model output are the monomer-composition ratios, particularly **scl-based PHAs** (especially **3HB**) and **mcl-based PHAs**, which exert the strongest positive or negative shifts in the prediction. Overall, the SHAP results confirm that the model bases its predictions on chemically meaningful structure–property relationships, reflecting known dependencies on monomer composition and molecular characteristics.

3.1.3 Melting Temperature (T_m) Model for PHBV polymers

3.1.3.1 Dataset Composition and Input Features

This model was created to explore which physicochemical and formulation-related descriptors are suitable for predicting the melting temperature (T_m) of PHBV polymers. The following input features were included:

Table 9. Input Features Used in the T_m Model.

Category	Input Feature	Type	Units
Composition	3-hydroxybutyrate (3HB) percentage	Numerical	%
Composition	3-hydroxyvalerate (3HV) percentage	Numerical	%

Molecular properties	Weight-average molar mass (Mw) of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate, PHBV)	Numerical	g/mol
Structural properties	Crystallinity index	Numerical	%
Additives	Additive type	Categorical	-
Additives	Additive percentage	Numerical	%

The initial dataset consisted of **181 samples**. Outlier detection was performed using the IQR method, after which **148 samples** remained. The Kennard-Stone algorithm was then used to ensure an even coverage of the descriptor space. Following a standard 80/20 split:

- Training set: 118 samples
- Test set: 30 samples

Table 10 summarizes the structure of the final dataset used for evaluation of the T_m prediction model.

Table 10. Sample rows from the final T_m dataset.

HB_ratio	HV_ratio	Mw_PHBV	Additive1_type	Additive1_percentage	Crystallinity_index	T_m _final
100.0	0.0	440000.0	Compatibilizer	10.0	61.00	447.15
100.0	0.0	440000.0	Compatibilizer	20.0	58.00	446.15
100.0	0.0	440000.0	Compatibilizer	40.0	53.00	443.15
100.0	0.0	440000.0	Compatibilizer	50.0	23.00	440.15
100.0	0.0	440000.0	Compatibilizer	60.0	21.00	438.15
98.0	2.0	280000.0	not_applicable	0.0	65.35	443.68
98.0	2.0	280000.0	Reinforcement	2.5	65.78	440.95
98.0	2.0	280000.0	Reinforcement	5.0	68.28	441.96
98.0	2.0	280000.0	Reinforcement	10.0	64.01	442.21
98.0	2.0	280000.0	Compatibilizer	1.0	63.34	441.31
91.0	9.0	23900.0	not_applicable	0.0	65.40	448.85
91.0	9.0	23900.0	Antioxidant	0.1	64.30	451.25
91.0	9.0	23900.0	Antioxidant	0.3	67.20	450.65
91.0	9.0	23900.0	Antioxidant	0.5	69.00	448.25
91.0	9.0	23900.0	Antioxidant	1.0	69.50	450.15
91.0	9.0	23900.0	Antioxidant	3.0	67.50	449.35
100.0	0.0	490000.0	Plasticizer	10.0	58.90	443.45
93.0	7.0	4400000.0	not_applicable	0.0	60.90	443.15
93.0	7.0	4400000.0	not_applicable	0.0	63.70	443.15
93.0	7.0	4400000.0	not_applicable	0.0	60.80	443.15

3.1.3.2 Model Development and Hyperparameter Selection

A **RF Regressor** was used, implemented via Python and the following libraries:

- **jaqpotpy**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning
- **NumPy** and **Pandas**: for numerical operations and data manipulation
- **Scikit-learn**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning
- **prince**: for FAMD-based feature-space construction

The candidate parameter values, along with those selected based on the best cross-validation performance, as well as the model evaluation, are presented in the tables below.

Table 11. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for T_m Model.

Hyperparameter	Candidate Values Tested	Optimal Value
n_estimators	[30, 50, 100, 200, 300]	300
max_depth	[None, 10, 20, 30]	None
min_samples_split	[2, 5, 10]	2
min_samples_leaf	[1, 2, 4, 5, 10]	1

Table 12. Model T_m Performance

Predictions	Metric	Optimal Value
Train set	R^2	0.969
Test set		0.866
Cross validation 5-fold		0.762

The T_m prediction model exhibited strong predictive capability, achieving an excellent fit on the training set ($R^2 = 0.969$) and solid generalization on the test set ($R^2 = 0.866$). The cross-validated R^2 value of **0.762** indicates that the model remains stable across resampled subsets, confirming that its performance is not overly dependent on a particular data split. Overall, the results demonstrate a reliable and well-generalized model suitable for T_m prediction.

3.1.3.3 Plot Results

The following figures present the comparison between the model predictions and the experimental values for the training and test sets.

Figure 7. Comparison plot of the predicted T_m values from the model with the observed values in the training set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.

Figure 8. Comparison plot of the predicted T_m values from the model with the observed values in the test set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.

3.1.3.4 SHAP Explainability Analysis

SHAP analysis was performed to identify which descriptors influence the predicted T_m values as presented in figure below.

Figure 9. SHAP Summary Plot for T_m Model.

The SHAP results indicate that **HV ratio** and **HB ratio** are the most influential descriptors for the model, with higher HV values generally increasing the prediction and higher HB values pushing the output downward. The **crystallinity index** also plays a key role, with higher crystallinity associated with higher predicted values, reflecting reduced chain mobility in PHBV-rich domains. **M_w** shows a moderate positive contribution, consistent with expected polymer-chain behaviour. Overall, the SHAP profile demonstrates that the model captures chemically and structurally meaningful trends, reinforcing confidence in its predictive robustness.

3.1.4 T_m Model for mcl-PHA polymers

3.1.4.1 Dataset Composition and Input Features

This model was created to explore which physicochemical and formulation-related descriptors are suitable for predicting the T_m of mcl-based PHA polymers. The following input features were included:

Table 13. Input Features Used in the T_m Model.

Category	Input Feature	Type	Units
Composition	Short-Chain-Length Monomer	Numerical	%
	Ratio in PHA		

Category	Input Feature	Type	Units
Composition	3-hydroxybutyrate (3HB) percentage	Numerical	%
Composition	3-hydroxyvalerate (3HV) percentage	Numerical	%
Composition	Medium-Chain-Length Monomer Ratio in PHA	Numerical	%
Molecular properties	Weight-average molar mass (Mw) of PHA polymer	Numerical	g/mol
Thermal properties	Glass transition temperature	Numerical	Kelvin

The initial dataset consisted of **257 samples**. Outlier detection was performed using the IQR method, after which **209 samples** remained. The Kennard-Stone algorithm was then used to ensure an even coverage of the descriptor space. Following a standard 80/20 split:

- Training set: 167 samples
- Test set: 42 samples

Table 14 summarizes the structure of the final dataset used for evaluation of the T_m prediction model.

Table 14. Sample rows from the final T_m dataset.

initial_scl pha_ratio	initial_3hb_ratio	initial_3hv_ratio	initial_mcl pha_ratio	mw	tg_final	tm_final
0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	124000.0	224.75	328.85
0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	145000.0	226.85	328.15
0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	110000.0	226.15	316.15
88.0	88.0	0.0	12.0	440000.0	275.15	383.15
0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	175000.0	239.15	331.15
0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	206000.0	233.15	332.15
0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	286000.0	240.05	331.25
99.1	99.1	0.0	0.9	260000.0	280.15	448.15
96.0	96.0	0.0	4.0	260000.0	277.15	438.15
96.0	96.0	0.0	4.0	170000.0	272.15	436.15
0.2	0.2	0.0	99.8	85000.0	234.15	325.15
0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	57000.0	231.75	328.45
0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	32000.0	228.05	313.75
0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	68000.0	230.25	318.25
0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	62000.0	226.45	325.35
0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	102000.0	226.15	338.75
0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	546400.0	236.06	321.13
0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	666300.0	235.44	321.16
0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	707800.0	234.88	321.02
0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	658900.0	234.77	320.81

3.1.4.2 Model Development and Hyperparameter Selection

A **RF Regressor** was used, implemented via Python and the following libraries:

- **jaqpotpy**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning
- **NumPy** and **Pandas**: for numerical operations and data manipulation
- **Scikit-learn**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning
- **prince**: for FAMD-based feature-space construction

The candidate parameter values, along with those selected based on the best cross-validation performance, as well as the model evaluation, are presented in the tables below.

Table 15. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for T_m Model.

Hyperparameter	Candidate Values Tested	Optimal Value
n_estimators	[30, 50, 100, 200, 300]	100
max_depth	[None, 10, 20, 30]	10
min_samples_split	[2, 5, 10]	2
min_samples_leaf	[1, 2, 4, 5, 10]	2

Table 16. Model T_m Performance.

Predictions	Metric	Optimal Value
Train set	R^2	0.945
Test set		0.916
Cross validation 10-fold		0.706

The T_m prediction model demonstrated strong predictive capability, with a high coefficient of determination on the training set ($R^2 = 0.945$) and excellent generalization on the test set ($R^2 = 0.916$). The 10-fold cross-validated R^2 value of **0.706** indicates that the model maintains reasonable stability when evaluated across different data partitions, although the lower CV score suggests a slightly higher sensitivity to sample variability compared to the T_g models. Overall, the results confirm that the T_m model captures the underlying structure–property relationships effectively and performs reliably on unseen data.

3.1.4.3 Plot Results

The following figures present the comparison between the model predictions and the experimental values for the training and test sets.

Figure 10. Comparison plot of the predicted T_m values from the model with the observed values in the training set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.

Figure 11. Comparison plot of the predicted T_m values from the model with the observed values in the test set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.

3.1.4.4 SHAP Explainability Analysis

SHAP analysis was performed to identify which descriptors influence the predicted T_m values as presented in figure below.

Figure 12. SHAP Summary Plot for T_g Model.

The SHAP analysis shows that **scl-based PHAs** (especially **3HB**) ratio are the strongest positive contributors to the predictive value, with higher values substantially increasing the T_m . In contrast, **scl-based PHAs** ratio has a negative effect, lowering T_m due to the increased chain flexibility introduced by medium-chain-length monomers. **Mw** exhibits a moderate positive contribution, consistent with reduced segmental mobility in longer chains. Finally, **T_g** and **3HV ratio** show smaller but meaningful influences, confirming that the model captures realistic structure–property relationships.

3.2 Mechanical and Rheological Models

3.2.1 Tensile Strength Model for PHBV polymers

3.2.1.1 Dataset Composition and Input Features

This model was created to explore which physicochemical and formulation-related descriptors are suitable for predicting the tensile strength of PHBV polymers. The following input features were included:

Table 17. Input Features Used in the Tensile Strength Model.

Category	Input Feature	Type	Units
Composition	3-hydroxybutyrate (3HB) percentage	Numerical	%
Molecular properties	Weight-average molar mass (Mw) of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate, PHBV)	Numerical	g/mol
Additives	Additive type	Categorical	-
Additives	Additive percentage	Numerical	%

The initial dataset consisted of **160 samples**. However, applying the IQR method for outlier detection did not lead to satisfactory model performance, as the procedure disproportionately removed valid but sparse observations and reduced the representation of rare categorical classes. To address this, the categorical descriptors were manually inspected, and categories with frequency under a certain limit were excluded.

Due to the skewed distribution of the target variable, where only a few samples occupied the upper range (Figure 13), simple outlier removal was insufficient. Instead, samples belonging to rare but meaningful categories were duplicated, and a small amount of controlled stochastic noise was added only to the input features. This approach improves feature diversity without corrupting the true target values. Adding noise to the target variable is generally discouraged, as it degrades the learning signal and introduces unnecessary label uncertainty (Goodfellow, Bengio & Courville, 2016).

Figure 13. Distribution of Tensile Strength Values in the Initial Dataset.

After constructing this augmented but scientifically consistent dataset which consisted of **215 samples**, the Kennard–Stone algorithm was applied to ensure an even coverage of the descriptor space. Following a standard 80/20 split:

- Training set: 172 samples
- Test set: 43 samples

Table 18 summarizes the structure of the final dataset used for evaluation of the Tensile Strength prediction model.

Table 18. Sample rows from the final Tensile Strength dataset.

HB_ratio	Mw_PHBV	Additive1_type	Additive1_percentage	Tensile_strength
97.5	280000.0	Antioxidant	2.5	20.60
97.5	280000.0	Antioxidant	5.0	21.30
97.5	280000.0	Antioxidant	10.0	28.30
97.5	280000.0	Antioxidant	15.0	26.50
100.0	825000.0	not_applicable	0.0	14.00
100.0	825000.0	Plasticizer	25.0	7.50
100.0	825000.0	Plasticizer	30.0	6.30
100.0	825000.0	Plasticizer	35.0	5.10
100.0	825000.0	Plasticizer	40.0	4.50
100.0	825000.0	Plasticizer	10.0	14.30
100.0	825000.0	Plasticizer	20.0	10.20
100.0	825000.0	Plasticizer	25.0	9.50
100.0	825000.0	Plasticizer	30.0	6.10
98.0	280000.0	not_applicable	0.0	27.40
98.0	280000.0	Reinforcement	2.5	22.20
98.0	280000.0	Reinforcement	5.0	21.60
98.0	280000.0	Reinforcement	10.0	20.10
91.0	23900.0	not_applicable	0.0	21.58
91.0	23900.0	Antioxidant	0.1	21.30
91.0	23900.0	Antioxidant	0.3	21.44

3.2.1.2 Model Development and Hyperparameter Selection

A **RF Regressor** was used, implemented via Python and the following libraries:

- **jaqpotpy**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning
- **NumPy** and **Pandas**: for numerical operations and data manipulation
- **Scikit-learn**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning
- **prince**: for FAMD-based feature-space construction

The candidate parameter values, along with those selected based on the best cross-validation performance, as well as the model evaluation, are presented in the tables below.

Table 19. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for Tensile Strength Model.

Hyperparameter	Candidate Values Tested	Optimal Value
n_estimators	[30, 50, 100, 200, 300]	30
max_depth	[None, 10, 20, 30]	None
min_samples_split	[2, 5, 10]	2
min_samples_leaf	[1, 2, 4, 5, 10]	5

Table 20. Model Tensile Strength Performance

Predictions	Metric	Optimal Value
Train set	R ²	0.955
Test set		0.964
Cross validation 10-fold		0.826

The tensile strength prediction model showed excellent performance, achieving a very high R² of **0.955** on the training set and a strong generalization ability with an R² of **0.964** on the test set. The 10-fold cross-validation R² of **0.826** further confirms that the model is stable, robust, and not overly dependent on a particular data split. Overall, these results indicate that the model captures the underlying mechanical behaviour of the materials effectively.

3.2.1.3 Plot Results

The following figures present the comparison between the model predictions and the experimental values for the training and test sets.

Figure 14. Comparison plot of the predicted tensile strength values from the model with the observed values in the training set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.

Figure 15. Comparison plot of the predicted tensile strength values from the model with the observed values in the test set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.

3.2.1.4 SHAP Explainability Analysis

SHAP analysis was performed to identify which descriptors influence the predicted tensile strength values as presented in figure below.

Figure 16. SHAP Summary Plot for Tensile Strength Model.

The SHAP analysis shows that **Mw** is the dominant driver of tensile strength, with higher Mw strongly increasing predicted strength. **Additive percentage** also contributes positively, especially at higher values. **The HB ratio** has a moderate but consistent influence on strengthening behaviour. Additive-type variables (plasticizer, antioxidant, reinforcement) show smaller effects, indicating limited formulation-specific effects.

3.2.2 Complex Viscosity Model for PHBV polymers

3.2.2.1 Dataset Composition and Input Features

This model was created to explore which physicochemical and formulation-related descriptors are suitable for predicting the complex viscosity of PHBV polymers. The following input features were included:

Table 21. Input Features Used in the Complex Viscosity Model.

Category	Input Feature	Type	Units
Composition	3-hydroxybutyrate (3HB) percentage	Numerical	%
Composition	3-hydroxyvalerate (3HV) percentage	Numerical	%

Category	Input Feature	Type	Units
Molecular properties	Weight-average molar mass (Mw) of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate, PHBV)	Numerical	g/mol
Experimental properties	Experimental temperature	Numerical	Kelvin
Experimental properties	Angular frequency of experiment	Numerical	rad/s
Additives	Additive type	Categorical	-
Additives	Additive percentage	Numerical	%

The initial dataset consisted of **1806 samples**. Outlier detection was performed using the IQR method, after which **788 samples** remained. The Kennard-Stone algorithm was then used to ensure an even coverage of the descriptor space. Following a standard 80/20 split:

- Training set: 630 samples
- Test set: 158 samples

Table 22 summarizes the structure of the final dataset used for evaluation of the Complex Viscosity prediction model.

Table 22. Sample rows from the final Complex Viscosity dataset.

angular_frequency_rad/s	Mw_PHBV	Additive1_type	Additive1_percentage	HB_ratio_formulation	HV_ratio_formulation	Temp	complex_viscosity
2.168554	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	297.313265
2.797747	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	272.905259
3.574304	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	272.905259
4.702626	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	259.233114
6.126805	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	254.829675
7.751071	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	254.829675
10.298310	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	246.245922
13.028476	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	237.951307
16.644724	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	226.030303
21.899063	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	222.190860
27.704683	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	218.416636
35.049421	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	207.474289
45.664054	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	193.732455
59.493304	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	184.026748
77.510708	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	171.837936
99.024961	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	157.730858
129.014433	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	155.051578
163.217213	117869.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	448.15	142.322581
62.831850	450000.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	463.15	419.007911
125.663700	450000.0	not_applicable	0.0	100.0	0.0	463.15	334.965439

3.2.2.2 Model Development and Hyperparameter Selection

A **RF Regressor** was used, implemented via Python and the following libraries:

- **jaqpotpy**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning
- **NumPy** and **Pandas**: for numerical operations and data manipulation
- **Scikit-learn**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning
- **prince**: for FAMD-based feature-space construction

The candidate parameter values, along with those selected based on the best cross-validation performance, as well as the model evaluation, are presented in the tables below.

Table 23. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for Complex Viscosity Model.

Hyperparameter	Candidate Values Tested	Optimal Value
n_estimators	[30, 50, 100, 200, 300]	300
max_depth	[None, 10, 20, 30]	None
min_samples_split	[2, 5, 10]	2
min_samples_leaf	[1, 2, 4, 5, 10]	1

Table 24. Model Complex Viscosity Performance.

Predictions	Metric	Optimal Value
Train set	R ²	0.983
Test set		0.861
Cross validation 10-fold		0.854

The complex viscosity prediction model showed excellent performance, achieving a very high R² of **0.983** on the training set and a strong generalization ability with an R² of **0.861** on the test set. The 10-fold cross-validation R² of **0.854** further confirms that the model is stable, robust, and not overly dependent on a particular data split. Overall, these results indicate that the model captures the underlying rheological behaviour of the materials effectively.

3.2.2.3 Plot Results

The following figures present the comparison between the model predictions and the experimental values for the training and test sets.

Figure 17. Comparison plot of the predicted complex viscosity values from the model with the observed values in the training set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.

Figure 18. Comparison plot of the predicted complex viscosity values from the model with the observed values in the test set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.

3.2.2.4 SHAP Explainability Analysis

SHAP analysis was performed to identify which descriptors influence the predicted complex viscosity values as presented in figure below.

Figure 19. SHAP Summary Plot for Complex Viscosity Model.

The SHAP analysis shows that **angular frequency** and **Mw** are the primary drivers of complex viscosity, with higher values strongly increasing the predicted viscosity. The **HV** and **HB ratios** also have meaningful effects, reflecting how monomer composition influences melting behaviour. **Temperature** displays a clear negative contribution, consistent with the expected decrease of viscosity at higher temperatures. **Additive-related features** have smaller but still detectable effects. Overall, the model captures physically consistent rheological relationships.

3.3 Biodegradation and Toxicity Models

3.3.1 Biodegradation Model for PHBV polymers

3.3.1.1 Dataset Composition and Input Features

This model was created to explore which physicochemical and formulation-related descriptors are suitable for predicting the biodegradation percentage of PHBV polymers. The following input features were included:

Table 25. Input Features Used in the Biodegradation Percentage Model.

Category	Input Feature	Type	Units
Composition	3-hydroxybutyrate (3HB) percentage	Numerical	%
Composition	3-hydroxyvalerate (3HV) percentage	Numerical	%
Experimental properties	Biodegradation time	Numerical	days
Experimental properties	Biodegradation temperature	Numerical	°C
Experimental properties	Biodegradation condition	Categorical	-
Experimental properties	Biodegradation mechanism	Categorical	-
Additives	Additive type	Categorical	-
Additives	Additive percentage	Numerical	%

The initial dataset consisted of **1222 samples**. Outlier detection was performed using the IQR method, after which **536 samples** remained. The Kennard-Stone algorithm was then used to ensure an even coverage of the descriptor space. Following a standard 80/20 split:

- Training set: 428 samples
- Test set: 108 samples

Table 26 summarizes the structure of the final dataset used for evaluation of the Biodegradation prediction model.

Table 26. Sample rows from the final Biodegradation dataset.

Adjusted_HB_ratio_formulation_mol	Adjusted_HV_ratio_formulation_mol	Biodegradation_time_days	Biodegradation_condition	Degradation_mechanism	T_biodeg	Degradation_Environment	Additive_type_1	Additive1_percentage_wt	Additive_type_2	Additive2_percentage_wt	Biodegradation_percentage
98.0	2.0	62.23529	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	95.59011
98.0	2.0	73.29412	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	96.13260
98.0	2.0	79.64706	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	97.23757
98.0	2.0	49.76471	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	96.96133
78.4	1.6	5.17647	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	filler	20.0	not_applicable	0.0	9.94475
78.4	1.6	8.47059	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	filler	20.0	not_applicable	0.0	18.78453
78.4	1.6	12.00000	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	filler	20.0	not_applicable	0.0	25.69061
78.4	1.6	16.23529	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	filler	20.0	not_applicable	0.0	40.60773
78.4	1.6	20.58824	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	filler	20.0	not_applicable	0.0	55.24862
78.4	1.6	25.76471	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	filler	20.0	not_applicable	0.0	73.20442
78.4	1.6	33.41176	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	filler	20.0	not_applicable	0.0	89.77901
78.4	1.6	36.94118	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	filler	20.0	not_applicable	0.0	93.09392
78.4	1.6	43.05882	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	filler	20.0	not_applicable	0.0	95.02762
78.4	1.6	50.00000	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	filler	20.0	not_applicable	0.0	94.75138
78.4	1.6	54.58824	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	filler	20.0	not_applicable	0.0	96.13260
78.4	1.6	62.23529	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	filler	20.0	not_applicable	0.0	96.40884
78.4	1.6	72.58824	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	filler	20.0	not_applicable	0.0	97.79006
78.4	1.6	79.29412	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	filler	20.0	not_applicable	0.0	99.72376
78.4	1.6	4.82353	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	filler	20.0	not_applicable	0.0	7.18232
78.4	1.6	7.76471	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28.0	soil	filler	20.0	not_applicable	0.0	15.46961

3.3.1.2 Model Development and Hyperparameter Selection

A **RF Regressor** was used, implemented via Python and the following libraries:

- **jaqpotpy**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning
- **NumPy** and **Pandas**: for numerical operations and data manipulation
- **Scikit-learn**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning
- **prince**: for FAMD-based feature-space construction

The candidate parameter values, along with those selected based on the best cross-validation performance, as well as the model evaluation, are presented in the tables below.

Table 27. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for Biodegradation Percentage Model.

Hyperparameter	Candidate Values Tested	Optimal Value
n_estimators	[30, 50, 100, 200, 300]	300
max_depth	[None, 10, 20, 30]	None
min_samples_split	[2, 5, 10]	2
min_samples_leaf	[1, 2, 4, 5, 10]	1

Table 28. Model Biodegradation Percentage Performance

Predictions	Metric	Optimal Value
Train set	R ²	0.997
Test set		0.980
Cross validation 10-fold		0.977

The biodegradation prediction model shows excellent performance, with an almost perfect fit on the training set ($R^2 = 0.997$) and equally strong generalization on the test set ($R^2 = 0.980$). The 10-fold cross-validation R^2 of **0.977** demonstrates remarkable stability across resampled subsets, indicating that the model is robust, not overfitted, and capable of delivering consistently reliable predictions across varying data partitions.

3.3.1.3 Plot Results

The following figures present the comparison between the model predictions and the experimental values for the training and test sets.

Figure 20. Comparison plot of the predicted biodegradation percentage values from the model with the observed values in the training set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.

Figure 21. Comparison plot of the predicted biodegradation percentage values from the model with the observed values in the test set. The red dashed line represents the $y=x$ line, where the predicted values are equal to the experimental ones.

3.3.1.4 SHAP Explainability Analysis

SHAP analysis was performed to identify which descriptors influence the predicted biodegradation percentage values as presented in figure below.

Figure 22. SHAP Summary Plot for Biodegradation Percentage Model

The SHAP analysis shows that **biodegradation time** is the dominant factor influencing the model, with longer durations driving stronger changes in the predicted biodegradation response. **Degradation mechanisms** (such as surface erosion and hydrolysis-assisted assimilation) also contribute substantially, highlighting how different biological pathways affect material breakdown. **Environmental conditions** like aerobic or anaerobic settings and soil exposure further shape the predictions, aligning with known biodegradation behaviors. **Additive-related features** have smaller effects, reflecting their secondary but still relevant role in modifying degradation performance. Overall, the model captures meaningful and physically consistent relationships within the biodegradation system.

3.3.2 Ecotoxicity Model for PHBV polymers

3.3.2.1 Dataset Composition and Input Features

This model was created to explore which physicochemical and formulation-related descriptors are suitable for predicting the ecotoxicity of PHBV polymers. The following input features were included:

Table 29. Input Features Used in the Ecotoxicity Model.

Category	Input Feature	Type	Units
Composition	3-hydroxybutyrate (3HB) percentage	Numerical	%
Composition	3-hydroxyvalerate (3HV) percentage	Numerical	%
Composition	4-hydroxyvalerate (4HV) percentage	Numerical	%
Experimental properties	Observation period	Numerical	days
Experimental properties	Species group	Categorical	-
Additives	Additive type	Categorical	-
Additives	Additive percentage	Numerical	%

The initial dataset consisted of **82 samples**. Due to the small sample size and sparse representation of several categories, no IQR outlier removal was applied to avoid losing informative minority cases. Instead, a manual inspection was performed to identify inconsistencies in categorical labels. The class '**Toxic**' was removed because it was represented by only a small number of samples, resulting in unstable model behavior and unreliable cross-validation. After removal, the dataset contained **72 samples**, with the target variable limited to two biologically meaningful categories: **Non-Toxic** and **Moderately Toxic**.

In contrast to the previous regression models, the Kennard–Stone algorithm was not used. The data were split using **stratified sampling**, a procedure widely recommended for classification tasks to maintain label distribution across folds and avoid biased model estimates (Goodfellow et al., 2016). Following a standard 80/20 split:

- Training set: 57 samples
- Test set: 15 samples

Table 30 summarizes the structure of the final dataset used for evaluation of the Ecotoxicity prediction model.

Table 30. Sample rows from the final Ecotoxicity dataset.

3HB_ratio	3HV_ratio	4HV_ratio	Observation_Period	Species_Group	Additive1_Percentage	Additive1_Use	Additive2_Percentage	Additive2_Use	Additive3_Percentage	Additive3_Use	Toxicity_Classification
100.0	0.0	0.0	4.000000	Aquatic_Organisms	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Moderately_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	4.000000	Aquatic_Organisms	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Non_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	4.000000	Aquatic_Organisms	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Moderately_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	4.000000	Aquatic_Organisms	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Moderately_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	28.000000	Terrestrial_Plant	72.0	Polymer_Matrix	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Moderately_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	21.000000	Terrestrial_Plant	72.0	Polymer_Matrix	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Moderately_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	28.000000	Terrestrial_Plant	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Non_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	28.000000	Terrestrial_Plant	50.0	Flexibilizer	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Non_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	28.000000	Terrestrial_Plant	50.0	Structural	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Non_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	183.000000	Terrestrial_Plant	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Non_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	183.000000	Terrestrial_Plant	50.0	Flexibilizer	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Non_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	183.000000	Terrestrial_Plant	50.0	Structural	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Non_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	28.000000	Terrestrial_Plant	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Non_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	28.000000	Terrestrial_Plant	50.0	Flexibilizer	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Non_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	28.000000	Terrestrial_Plant	50.0	Structural	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Non_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	183.000000	Terrestrial_Plant	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Non_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	183.000000	Terrestrial_Plant	50.0	Flexibilizer	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Non_Toxic
100.0	0.0	0.0	183.000000	Terrestrial_Plant	50.0	Structural	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Non_Toxic
93.5	6.5	0.0	0.020833	Aquatic_Organisms	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Non_Toxic
93.5	6.5	0.0	3.000000	Aquatic_Organisms	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	0.0	not_applicable	Moderately_Toxic

3.3.2.2 Model Development and Hyperparameter Selection

A **RF Classifier** was used, implemented via Python and the following libraries:

- **jaqpotpy**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning
- **NumPy** and **Pandas**: for numerical operations and data manipulation
- **Scikit-learn**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning

The candidate parameter values, along with those selected based on the best cross-validation performance, as well as the model evaluation, are presented in the tables below.

Table 31. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for Ecotoxicity Model.

Hyperparameter	Candidate Values Tested	Optimal Value
n_estimators	[20, 40, 50, 100]	20
max_depth	[None, 10, 20, 30]	None
min_samples_split	[2, 5, 10]	2
min_samples_leaf	[1, 2, 4, 5, 10]	1
Max_features	["sqrt", "log"]	"sqrt"

Table 32. Model Ecotoxicity Performance.

Predictions	Metric	Optimal Value
Train set	Balanced Accuracy	0.948
	macro-F1	0.947
Test set	Balanced Accuracy	0.937
	macro-F1	0.933

Cross validation 5-fold	Balanced Accuracy	0.811
	macro-F1	0.802

The ecotoxicity classification model demonstrates strong predictive performance. On the training set, it achieved a **balanced accuracy of 0.948** and a **macro-F1 score of 0.947**, indicating that the classifier successfully learned the toxicity patterns without collapsing toward the majority class. Evaluation on the unseen test set produced similarly high results (**balanced accuracy = 0.937**, **macro-F1 = 0.933**), which confirms that the model generalizes well and retains class-sensitive behaviour outside the training distribution. The 5-fold cross-validation **balanced accuracy of 0.811** and **macro-F1 of 0.802** further illustrates the model's robustness across resampled subsets of the data, suggesting stable performance under varying partitions and no signs of overfitting. Overall, these results indicate that the ecotoxicity model is a reliable classifier capable of providing consistent toxicity assessments.

3.3.2.3 SHAP Explainability Analysis

SHAP analysis was performed to identify which descriptors influence the predicted ecotoxicity as presented in figure below.

Figure 23. SHAP Summary Plot for Ecotoxicity Model.

The SHAP analysis reveals that **species-related features** (especially Terrestrial Plant and Air-Breathing Animals) exert the strongest influence on the model's predictions. Samples associated with terrestrial plants tend to push the model toward the **Non-Toxic** class (negative SHAP values), while those related to air-breathing organisms increase the likelihood of **Moderately Toxic** predictions, indicating biological sensitivity differences across species groups. **Observation period** also contributes significantly, with longer exposure durations generally associated with higher

ecotoxic response. Polymer composition features show moderate influence, suggesting that material chemistry affects how organisms respond to polymer systems. In contrast, additive-related variables display smaller but consistent contributions, indicating secondary effects on toxicity rather than dominant drivers. Overall, the model captures ecologically meaningful patterns, reflecting how organism type, exposure duration, and polymer composition jointly influence toxicity responses.

3.3.3 Cytotoxicity Model for PHBV polymers

3.3.3.1 Dataset Composition and Input Features

This model was created to explore which physicochemical and formulation-related descriptors are suitable for predicting the cytotoxicity of PHBV polymers. The following input features were included:

Table 33. Input Features Used in the Cytotoxicity Model.

Category	Input Feature	Type	Units
Composition	3-hydroxybutyrate (3HB) percentage	Numerical	%
Composition	3-hydroxyvalerate (3HV) percentage	Numerical	%
Experimental properties	Concentration	Numerical	mg/L
Experimental properties	Incubation time	Numerical	days
Additives	Additive type	Categorical	-
Additives	Additive percentage	Numerical	%

The initial dataset consisted of **206 samples**. Outlier detection was performed using the IQR method, after which **81 samples** remained. Because the task is a classification problem, the dataset was split using stratification to maintain the class's distribution. Following an 80/20 split:

- Training set: 64 samples
- Test set: 17 samples

Table 34 summarizes the structure of the final dataset used for evaluation of the Cytotoxicity prediction model.

Table 34. Sample rows from the final Cytotoxicity dataset.

hb_ratio	hv_ratio	incubation_time	concentration	additive1_percentage	additive1_use	additive2_percentage	additive2_use	additive3_percentage	additive3_use	toxicity
100.0	0.0	24.0	1.3	32.90	targeting_ligand	32.90	stabilizer	1.32	active_drug	non-toxic
100.0	0.0	24.0	3.0	32.90	targeting_ligand	32.90	stabilizer	1.32	active_drug	toxic
100.0	0.0	24.0	6.0	32.90	targeting_ligand	32.90	stabilizer	1.32	active_drug	non-toxic
100.0	0.0	48.0	0.0	32.90	targeting_ligand	32.90	stabilizer	1.32	active_drug	non-toxic
100.0	0.0	48.0	0.2	32.90	targeting_ligand	32.90	stabilizer	1.32	active_drug	non-toxic
100.0	0.0	48.0	0.6	32.90	targeting_ligand	32.90	stabilizer	1.32	active_drug	toxic
100.0	0.0	48.0	1.3	32.90	targeting_ligand	32.90	stabilizer	1.32	active_drug	toxic
100.0	0.0	48.0	3.0	32.90	targeting_ligand	32.90	stabilizer	1.32	active_drug	toxic
100.0	0.0	48.0	6.0	32.90	targeting_ligand	32.90	stabilizer	1.32	active_drug	toxic
100.0	0.0	72.0	0.0	32.90	targeting_ligand	32.90	stabilizer	1.32	active_drug	non-toxic
100.0	0.0	72.0	0.2	32.90	targeting_ligand	32.90	stabilizer	1.32	active_drug	toxic
100.0	0.0	72.0	0.6	32.90	targeting_ligand	32.90	stabilizer	1.32	active_drug	toxic
100.0	0.0	72.0	1.3	32.90	targeting_ligand	32.90	stabilizer	1.32	active_drug	toxic
100.0	0.0	72.0	3.0	32.90	targeting_ligand	32.90	stabilizer	1.32	active_drug	toxic
100.0	0.0	72.0	6.0	32.90	targeting_ligand	32.90	stabilizer	1.32	active_drug	toxic
85.0	15.0	24.0	0.0	33.33	targeting_ligand	33.33	stabilizer	0.00	not_applicable	non-toxic
85.0	15.0	24.0	0.2	33.33	targeting_ligand	33.33	stabilizer	0.00	not_applicable	non-toxic
85.0	15.0	24.0	0.6	33.33	targeting_ligand	33.33	stabilizer	0.00	not_applicable	non-toxic
85.0	15.0	24.0	1.3	33.33	targeting_ligand	33.33	stabilizer	0.00	not_applicable	non-toxic
85.0	15.0	24.0	3.0	33.33	targeting_ligand	33.33	stabilizer	0.00	not_applicable	non-toxic

3.3.3.2 Model Development and Hyperparameter Selection

A **RF Classifier** was used, implemented via Python and the following libraries:

- **jaqpotpy**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning
- **NumPy** and **Pandas**: for numerical operations and data manipulation
- **Scikit-learn**: for model construction and hyperparameter tuning

The candidate parameter values, along with those selected based on the best cross-validation performance, as well as the model evaluation, are presented in the tables below.

Table 35. Hyperparameter Grid and Selected Optimal Values for Cytotoxicity Model.

Hyperparameter	Candidate Values Tested	Optimal Value
n_estimators	[20, 40, 50, 100, 200]	200
max_depth	[None, 10, 20, 30]	None
min_samples_split	[2, 5, 10]	5
min_samples_leaf	[1, 2, 4, 5, 10]	2
Max_features	["sqrt", "log"]	"sqrt"

Table 36. Model Cytotoxicity Performance.

Predictions	Metric	Optimal Value
Train set	Balanced Accuracy	0.929
	macro-F1	0.929

Test set	Balanced Accuracy	0.954
	macro-F1	0.938
Cross validation 5-fold	Balanced Accuracy	0.811
	macro-F1	0.793

The cytotoxicity classification model shows strong predictive performance. On the training set, it reached a **balanced accuracy of 0.929** and a **macro-F1 score of 0.929**, indicating effective learning of cytotoxic patterns without collapsing to the majority class. Test-set performance was even higher (**balanced accuracy = 0.954**, **macro-F1 = 0.938**), confirming good generalization and class-sensitive behaviour on unseen data. The 5-fold cross-validation results (**balanced accuracy = 0.811**, **macro-F1 = 0.793**) further support the model's robustness, demonstrating stable performance across different partitions.

3.3.3.3 SHAP Explainability Analysis

SHAP analysis was performed to identify which descriptors influence the predicted cytotoxicity as presented in figure below.

Figure 24. SHAP Summary Plot for Cytotoxicity Model.

The SHAP analysis shows that formulation-related variables play a dominant role in determining cytotoxicity outcomes. **Additive 2 percentage** is the most influential parameter, where higher proportions shift predictions toward the cytotoxic class (positive SHAP values), while lower percentages reduce predicted toxicity, highlighting its strong effect on cellular response. **Incubation time** and **concentration** also contribute substantially; longer exposure durations and higher material concentrations consistently increase predicted cytotoxicity, reflecting dose- and time-dependent biological effects. Finally, structural descriptors such as **HV** and **HB ratio** show minimal effects, implying that morphological variations are less critical than chemical formulation

and exposure conditions. Overall, the model captures mechanistically meaningful patterns: cytotoxicity is primarily driven by additive composition and exposure intensity.

3.3.4 Toxicity Statistical Analysis for mcl-PHAs

In this part of the Deliverable, the main objective was to develop predictive QSAR models for the safety (toxicity) profiles of target mcl-PHA formulations. The predictive model was meant to be developed at the AUA, using theoretically calculated descriptors (independent variables) from data libraries (see Deliverable 2.5) to determine associations with endpoints, for example a numerical toxicity value, such as LD₅₀, related to environmental safety (dependent variables) for target biomaterials.

However, the application of ML approaches is highly dependent on the availability and quality of sufficiently large, curated datasets. Recent reviews of predictive toxicology have highlighted that data variety and inconsistency remain significant barriers in developing robust models (Jeong & Choi, 2022). The volume and diversity of reliable toxicity data are often limited, particularly for novel biomaterials such as mcl-PHAs, for which standardized ecotoxicological endpoint datasets are rare (Richarz, 2019). Although major databases such as ToxCast/Tox21 provide extensive toxicity data for thousands of chemicals, these focus largely on small organic compounds rather than polymeric or complex biomaterials.

Consequently, despite the clear potential of QSAR and ML approaches, the limited and heterogeneous data available in literature hindered the development of statistically significant predictive models in this task. Given these limitations, only statistical analyses were performed to explore possible associations between the reported physicochemical parameters and the observed toxicity outcomes for mcl-PHAs. These analyses, although limited in scope, compared to data-driven ML modeling, offer valuable preliminary information and serve as a basis for future computational efforts.

3.3.4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics for the percentage (%) composition of monomers and polymer characteristics recorded in the database are presented in Table 37. The main monomers reported so far were 3HHx, 3HO, 3HHp, 3HN, 3HD and 3HDD, with the mean values of monomer composition being 18.54%, 9.57%, 21.97%, 8.01%, 10.10% and 3.63%, respectively. This indicates that the most dominant monomers in the formulations were 3HHx and 3HHp, while 3HDD was the one with the lowest values. The skewness (1.2- 2.5) and kurtosis (0.9- 2.9) indicate distributions that are slightly right-skewed, meaning that some compositions contained higher than the average ratios of certain monomers. Furthermore, the min-max ranges (0–100%) indicate that, in some compositions, the individual monomers were completely absent (e.g. 0%). Regarding the molecular characteristics of the polymer (Mn, Mw, PDI), the Number Average Molecular Weight (Mn) was ~133628 Da, the Weight Average Molecular Weight (Mw) was ~366894 Da, and the polydispersity index (PDI) was ~2.13. The fact that Mw > Mn and PDI ≈ 2.1 is typical for biosynthetic

mcl-PHAs, which usually have moderate polydispersity due to biological variability in chain termination and elongation processes. Additionally, the asymmetry values ($M_n \approx 1,0$; $M_w \approx 1,0$; $PDI = -0,82$) suggest that M_n and M_w are right-skewed, i.e. there were some polymers with very high molecular weight. On the contrary, the PDI is slightly left-skewed, meaning that in most cases the dispersion was slightly below average, with some samples showing values higher than average. Finally, the range (M_n : 10,000–333,000; M_w : 2,300–834,000) indicates that the polymer compositions range from low to high molecular weight, indicating differences in synthesis conditions or copolymer composition.

Table 37. Descriptive statistics of polymer composition ratios and molecular weight parameters.

Parameter	3HHx ratio (%)	3HO ratio (%)	3HHp ratio (%)	3HN ratio (%)	3HD ratio (%)	3HDD ratio (%)	Mn (Da)	Mw (Da)	PDI
Mean	18.54	9.57	21.97	8.01	10.10	3.63	133628	366894	2.13
Std. deviation	3.09	2.19	2.50	1.83	1.64	0.65	6681	58548	0.07
Median	0	0	0.49	0	0	0	141800	4600	2.20
Kurtosis	0.75	4.07	0.31	4.07	0.65	1.16	4	-2	-1.30
Skewness	1.64	2.45	1.27	2.45	1.59	1.76	1	0	-0.82
Min	0	0	0	0	0	0	10000	2300	1.80
Max	100	83.86	100	70.17	63.00	21.20	333000	834000	2.37
n	149	149	149	149	149	149	63	49	10

The dataset showed a significant imbalance in toxicity, with 89.93% of the formulations classified as non-toxic and only 10.07% as toxic (Figure 25a). This indicates that most mcl-PHAs, including some with additives, exhibited minimal toxic effects under the reported conditions. When toxicity was examined in relation to the presence of additives (Figures 25b-c), toxic reactions were observed more frequently in formulations containing additives (14.29%), suggesting that some additives may contribute to reduced cell compatibility.

Figure 25. Distribution of toxicity and relationship with additive presence in mcl-PHA formulations. a) Overall toxicity profile of mcl-PHAs. b) Toxicity distribution in formulations containing additives c) Toxicity distribution in formulations without additives.

Finally, the comparison of cell viability (Figure 26) further supports this observation: the non-toxic formulations achieved a mean viability of $\sim 100.5\%$, while the toxic formulations showed a significantly lower mean viability of $\sim 56.7\%$, highlighting a significant difference in biological response. Therefore, these results show that the mcl-PHA dataset is synthetically diverse but mostly biocompatible.

Figure 26. Cell viability comparison between toxic and non-toxic mcl-PHA formulations.

4 Conclusions

The work conducted in Deliverable **D2.5** successfully established a suite of ML models capable of predicting key physicochemical, rheological, biodegradation, cytotoxicity, and ecotoxicity properties of scl- and mcl-based PHA materials. By implementing a rigorous and transparent workflow which includes mixed-data dimensionality reduction (FAMD method), robust outlier detection (IQR method), model training, hyperparameter optimization, AD assessment and SHAP-based explainability, the developed predictive tools achieve high accuracy and scientific credibility while remaining computationally lightweight and user accessible.

Across all models, performance was consistently strong: regression models for T_g , T_m , tensile strength, complex viscosity, and biodegradation displayed high R^2 values and stable cross-validation results, demonstrating their ability to capture nonlinear structure-property relationships inherent to polymer systems. The cytotoxicity and ecotoxicity classification models delivered equally strong predictive capability, with balanced accuracy and macro-F1 scores confirming reliable behaviour across minority classes and generalization beyond the training distribution. Explainability of SHAP-based analyses further validated that the models base their predictions on physically and biologically meaningful descriptors.

Toxicity Statistical Analysis for mcl-PHAs was also performed due to the limited and heterogeneous data available in literature which hindered the development of QSAR-based ML models in this task. Given these limitations, only statistical analyses were performed to explore possible associations between the reported physicochemical parameters and the observed toxicity outcomes for mcl-PHAs. This indicated that most mcl-PHAs, including some with additives, exhibited minimal toxic effects under the reported conditions and were mainly biocompatible. Because only limited data were also available in the literature regarding the biodegradation behavior of mcl-based materials, ongoing experiments at the AUA laboratory facilities aim to provide deeper insight into their degradation mechanisms. Regarding the mcl-PHAs' mechanical and rheological properties, the available literature data were limited and highly heterogeneous, which hindered the development of QSAR-based ML models in this task. In the ongoing WP3, we can leverage the partners' experimental data on these properties to develop more robust predictive models.

Importantly, all final models were deployed on the Jaqpot platform (<https://jaqpot.org>), ensuring traceability, reproducibility, and ease of use for consortium partners. This digital deployment transforms the modelling work into a practical decision-support framework, enabling rapid, low-cost prediction of polymer performance in humanitarian contexts where experimental characterization is often constrained by time, resources, and laboratory infrastructure.

Overall, the **ANIPH AI predictive tool** demonstrates that ML can robustly accelerate the design, assessment, and responsible use of biodegradable materials. The models developed provide a

scientifically grounded foundation for future optimization, integration of new data and expansion toward broader polymer classes, contributing directly to ANIPH's mission of reducing environmental and biological risks associated with plastic materials.

This deliverable is a key component toward achieving Milestone 3 (*'ANIPH AI Predictive System and IT platform/tools ready'*). It provides essential inputs and functionalities required for the system to reach full operational readiness.

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6 Annexes

6.1 Annex 1 – Source Code and Processed Datasets for the ANIPH Predictive Models

This annex documents the location and structure of the source code and processed datasets used to develop the ANIPH machine-learning models described in this deliverable. All scripts, Jupyter notebooks and curated datasets have been deposited in a public GitHub repository to ensure transparency, reproducibility and long-term accessibility.

The full codebase is available at:

GitHub repository <https://github.com/FSL-AUA/ANIPH-models>

6.2 Annex – 2 Jaqpot Access and Usage Instructions

6.2.1 Direct Access Links to ANIPH Models

Predicted Property	Model Type	Link
Melting temperature of PHBV polymers	Regression	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2299/description
Glass transition temperature of PHBV polymers	Regression	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2300/description
Biodegradation percentage of PHBV polymers	Regression	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2324/description
Tensile strength of PHBV polymers	Regression	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2321/description
Complex viscosity of PHBV polymers	Regression	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2291/description
Cytotoxicity of PHBV polymers	Classification	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2259/description
Ecotoxicity of PHBV polymers	Classification	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2244/description
Melting temperature of medium chain length PHA polymers	Regression	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2322/description
Glass transition temperature of medium chain length PHA polymers	Regression	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2297/description

6.2.2 Navigating the Jaqpot Platform

When a user opens a model through one of the links of the Table above, they are redirected to the model overview interface.

When opening the model page, the following tabs appear:

1. [Description](#)

The Description tab gives a short model summary and defines the prediction target.

Dashboard > Models > Glass transition temperature model (1) A.N.I.P.H.

Glass transition temperature model (1) A.N.I.P.H.

Alexandros Angelis @alexangelo 15 days ago SKLEARN_ONNX

Description Features Predict Metrics Edit Discussion

Predict glass transition temperature of PHBV polymers.

2. [Features](#)

The Features tab lists all **input features (independent variables)** and the **predicted output (dependent variable)**.

Dashboard > Models > Glass transition temperature model (1) A.N.I.P.H.

Glass transition temperature model (1) A.N.I.P.H.

Alexandros Angelis @alexangelo 15 days ago SKLEARN_ONNX

Description Features Predict Metrics Edit Discussion

Independent Features

Name	Units	Range	Description	Type	Actions
3-hydroxybutyrate (3HB) percentage	%			FLOAT	👁️ ✎️
3-hydroxyvalerate (3HV) percentage	%			FLOAT	👁️ ✎️
Weight-average molar mass (Mw) of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate, PHBV)	g/mol			FLOAT	👁️ ✎️
Additive 1 - type				CATEGORICAL	👁️ ✎️
Additive 1 - percentage	%			FLOAT	👁️ ✎️
Crystallinity index	%			FLOAT	👁️ ✎️

Dependent Features

Name	Units	Description	Type	Actions
Glass transition temperature	Kelvin		FLOAT	👁️ ✎️

For each feature, the interface specifies:

- Unit of measurement
- Brief description
- Valid range (when applicable)
- Variable type (numeric / categorical)

This tab should be consulted before running predictions to ensure correct formatting and consistent units.

3. [Predict](#)

The predict tab allows the user to run predictions. Two input modes are available:

- Form input

Numerical values are entered manually in the interface and categorical features are provided as dropdown menus.

Dashboard > Models > Glass transition temperature model (1) A.N.I.P.H.

Glass transition temperature model (1) A.N.I.P.H.

Alexandros Angelis @alexangelo 15 days ago SKLEARN_ONNX

Description Features **Predict** Metrics Edit Discussion

Choose Your Prediction Input Method

Fill out the form or Upload a CSV file (max 100 rows)

3-hydroxybutyrate (3HB) percentage * 80

3-hydroxyvalerate (3HV) percentage * 20

Weight-average molar mass (Mw) of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate, PHBV) * 15000

Additive 1 - type * Select Additive 1 - type

Additive 1 - percentage * Insert value...

Crystallinity index * Insert value...

Not applicable

Compatibilizer

Submit

- Batch upload

Multiple samples can be submitted at once using a .csv file.

Dashboard > Models > Glass transition temperature model (1) A.N.I.P.H.

Glass transition temperature model (1) A.N.I.P.H.

Alexandros Angelis @alexangelo 15 days ago SKLEARN_ONNX

Description Features **Predict** Metrics Edit Discussion

Choose Your Prediction Input Method

Fill out the form or Upload a CSV file (max 100 rows)

Upload the Input CSV

Choose File No file chosen

No file chosen

Submit Download sample CSV

Predictions are generated by pressing **Submit** and **Results** appear below the form.

Dashboard > Models > Glass transition temperature model (1) A.N.I.P.H.

Glass transition temperature model (1) A.N.I.P.H.

Alexandros Angelis @alexangelo 15 days ago SKLEARN_ONNX

Description Features **Predict** Metrics Edit Discussion

Choose Your Prediction Input Method

Fill out the form or Upload a CSV file (max 100 rows)

3-hydroxybutyrate (3HB) percentage 100

3-hydroxyvalerate (3HV) percentage 0

Weight-average molar mass (Mw) of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate, PHBV) 100000

Additive 1 - type Not applicable

Additive 1 - percentage 0

Crystallinity index 20

Submit

Result

ID 30704 Success

less than a minute ago less than 5 seconds

Export CSV

Rows per page 25

3-hydroxyvalerate (3HV) percentage	Weight-average molar mass (Mw) of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate, PHBV)	Additive 1 - type	Additive 1 - percentage	Crystallinity Index	Glass transition temperature	Applicability Domain
0	100000	Not applicable	0	20	269.07806396484375	In Domain

1

Each model includes an applicability domain check which indicates whether the input sample is within the model's training space. **Out of Domain** predictions may be unreliable and should be interpreted with caution.

4. [Metrics](#)

Metrics tab displays the model's performance indicators. Depending on the model type, this may include:

- Training metrics
- Test metrics
- Cross-validation metrics

The screenshot shows the 'Metrics' tab for a model named 'Glass transition temperature model (1) A.N.I.P.H.' created by Alexandros Angelis 15 days ago using SKLEARN_ONNX. The interface displays three sections of performance metrics:

- Train scores:**
 - TO_FINAL
 - R²: 0.9829408
 - MAE: 0.5447302
 - RMSE: 0.71554863
 - Folds: 1
- Test scores:**
 - TO_FINAL
 - R²: 0.87474597
 - MAE: 1.152169
 - RMSE: 1.6311315
 - Folds: 1
- Cross validation scores:**
 - TO_FINAL
 - R²: 0.83498263
 - MAE: 1.692384
 - RMSE: 2.1677434
 - Folds: 5

At the bottom, there is a 'Validate model' button with a 'Press to expand' prompt.

Regression models report **R²**, **MAE** and **RMSE**. Classification models typically report **balanced accuracy**, **F1-score**, **confusion matrices** or similar indicators.

5. Exporting predictions

After execution, results can be downloaded. Models provide .csv file export for both single and batch predictions.

Dashboard > Models > Glass transition temperature model (1) A.N.I.P.H.

Glass transition temperature model (1) A.N.I.P.H.

Alexandros Angelis @alexangelo 15 days ago SKLEARN_ONNX

Description Features Predict Metrics Edit Discussion

Choose Your Prediction Input Method

Fill out the form or Upload a CSV file (max 100 rows)

3-hydroxybutyrate (3HB) percentage * 100

3-hydroxyvalerate (3HV) percentage * 0

Weight-average molar mass (Mw) of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate, PHBV) * 100000

Additive 1 - type * Not applicable

Additive 1 - percentage * 0

Crystallinity index * 20

Submit

Result

ID 30705 Success

less than a minute ago less than 5 seconds

[Export CSV](#)

Total result Rows per page 25

3-hydroxybutyrate (3HB) percentage	3-hydroxyvalerate (3HV) percentage	Weight-average molar mass (Mw) of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate, PHBV)	Additive 1 - type	Additive 1 - percentage	Crystallinity Index	Glass trans
100	0	100000	Not applicab le	0	20	269.0780

1